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PRINCIPLES OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Annotation: This article is focused on developing language competencies: linguistic and communicative competencies by teaching grammar in the context using an inductive way of teaching by leading students from practice to theory. The teacher guides the students to notice the grammar pattern, and finally explicitly exposes them to it.

Keywords: native speaker, competence, goal, teaching four skills, cognitive, linguistic, speech etiquette, communicative, task-completion activities, puzzles, games, map-reading, motivational, Communicative Language teaching.

In the era of globalization, we realize that teaching language without authenticity from real-life aspects is like talking too much about any type of meal but do not allow to taste it. Our smart students also understand this and according to their progress of using English in communication, their results, and level of activity in classes we may see are we on the right way or not. So, we need to interact with authentic materials for a wider and deeper explanation of linguistics.

Every year in our country, several areas of knowledge are determined, the development of which is given priority attention. This year physics and foreign languages have become such areas.

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- The time has come to create in our country a new system of teaching foreign languages, which will become a solid foundation for the future. Since we set ourselves the goal of building a competitive state, from now on, graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges, and universities must be fluent in at least two foreign languages. This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the work of the head of each educational institution, said Shavkat Mirziyoyev on a video conference on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages was held on 6 May under the chairmanship of President.

Additionally, here the important place is assigned to methods of language teachers training, the basis of teaching four skills, and so on. It began to be implemented especially after the presidential decree 1875, which was accepted in December 2012.

Therefore, we should pay extensive attention earnestly to the young generation`s occupation of foreign languages to make tremendous progress in the future.

We may see great changes in the last few decades if we talk about teaching and learning languages. Nowadays, it demands not only knowing it by “knowledge” but also feeling and understanding it by our cognitive competence. It means that to know only the grammar and structure of the language is not enough. Language is beyond grammar rules and structures. And here comes for help different non-linguistic factors such as culture, lifestyle, shared norms, history and, other social circumstances.

But here is the difficulty of defining native speaker norms ‘in a time of large-scale migrations, cross-national and cross-cultural encounters, and increasing linguistic and pragmatic differences among speakers of the same language. Even if we can agree on what constitutes native-speaker competence, many questions how

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appropriate this model is to learners, both because it sets the impossible target of becoming like a native speaker, something which could potentially de-motivate learners and which devalues the social identity and competencies they have developed within their own culture, and because the communicative needs of non-native speakers are very different from native speakers existing in a particular speech community and vary according to the social context in which they wish to operate. The example given in the vignette just proves that such non-linguistic factors as mentality norms, speech etiquette, history, culture impact the speech greatly. One should take into consideration the above-mentioned factors if he wants to make his utterance clear and up to his expectations.

Knowing and feeling the language can help us to choose the appropriate language and be the fluent speaker of the language and to explore our own English within our notions. As a result, we invent our own English some of them which already exist, and named a World Englishes.

The term “competence” is derived from the concept of “performance” firstly proposed by Chomsky in the 1960s. The former is the linguistic knowledge of the idealized native speaker, an innate biological function of the mind that allows the speaker to generate the indefinite set of grammatical sentences that constitutes the target language whilst the latter is the actual use of language in concrete situations. However, according to Campbell and Wales (1970), Chomsky’s competence omitted the linguistic ability referring to the production or use of grammatically incorrect utterances, but appropriate to the context of the situational and verbal context of the utterance. Similarly, Hymes (1972) emphasized that in addition to linguistic competence, the language user has another intuitive system in which the rules of grammar would be useless. That is, he or she can adjust his or her language use based on factors like the topic, situation, and human relations. Based on his

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argument, he proposes the concept of “communicative competence” which includes both linguistic competence and implicit and explicit knowledge, both the rules of grammar and contextual or sociolinguistic knowledge of the rules of language use in contexts. To put it simply, Hymens states that communicative competence involves the following: what is formally possible, what is feasible, what is the social meaning or value of a given utterance, and what occurs.

Applied linguistics has for some time suggested that communicative competence includes a major competent, usually termed strategic competence, the development of which largely determines the learner’s fluency and conversational skills. Practicing teachers, however, are usually unaware of the significance of this competence, and hardly any activities have been developed to include strategy training in actual language teaching. This work aims to bridge the gap between theory and practice by first describing strategic competence and then presenting language exercises to facilitate its development. Communicative language teaching is aimed at improving the learner’s communicative competence. According to the widely accepted theory of Canale and Swain (1980), communicative competence as a whole can be explained in terms of three component competencies, grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, and strategic competence.

The communicative aspect of language use in social life will be related to communicative competence. Communicative competence refers to the competence to communicate (Bagaric and Djigunovic, 2007:94). It will highlight the use of language for communication (Louma, 2004:97). Due to these reasons, it can be said that communicative competence plays such an important role in daily life interaction. The success of reaching the goal of social interaction will depend on the large extent of ability within communicative competence (Rickheit and Strohner, 2008:15).

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The type of classroom activities proposed in CLT also implied new roles in the classroom for teachers and learners. Learners now have to participate in classroom activities that were based on a cooperative rather than individualistic approach to learning. Students have to become comfortable with listening to their peers in group work or pair work tasks, rather than relying on the teacher for a model. They were expected to take on a greater degree of responsibility for their learning. And teachers now have to assume the role of facilitator and monitor. Rather than being a model for correct speech and writing and one with the primary responsibility of making students produce plenty of error-free sentences, the teacher has to develop a different view of learners' errors and of her/his role in facilitating language learning.

One of the goals of CLT is to develop fluency in language use. Fluency is natural language use occurring when a speaker engages in meaningful interaction and maintains comprehensible and ongoing communication despite limitations in his or her communicative competence. Fluency is developed by creating classroom activities in which students must negotiate meaning, use communication strategies, correct misunderstandings, and work to avoid communication breakdowns. Fluency practice can be contrasted with accuracy practice, which focuses on creating correct examples of language use. Differences between activities that focus on fluency and those that focus on accuracy can be summarized as follows: Activities focusing on fluency is to reflect natural use of language, focusing on achieving communication, requiring meaningful use of language and communication strategies. Produce language that may not be predictable and seek to link language use to context. Activities focusing on accuracy can be reflecting classroom use of language and focusing on the formation of correct examples of language as well as practicing language out of context and small samples of language.

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Many other activity types can also be used in CLT including the following:

- Task-completion activities: puzzles, games, map-reading, and other kinds of classroom tasks in which the focus is on using one's language resources to complete a task.
- Information-gathering activities: student-conducted surveys, interviews, and searches in which students are required to use their linguistic resources to collect information.
- Opinion-sharing activities: activities in which students compare values, opinions, or beliefs, such as a ranking task in which students list six qualities in order of importance that they might consider in choosing a date or spouse.
- Information-transfer activities: These require learners to take information that is presented in one form, and represent it in a different form. For example, they may read instructions on how to get from A to B, and then draw a map showing the sequence, or they may read information about a subject and then represent it as a graph.
- Reasoning-gap activities: These involve deriving some new information from given information through the process of inference, practical reasoning, etc. For example, working out a teacher's timetable based on given class timetables.

As we know that communicative practice refers to activities where practice in using language within a real communicative context is the focus, where real information is exchanged, and where the language used is not predictable.

Most of the activities discussed above reflect an important aspect of classroom tasks in CLT, namely that they are designed to be carried out in pairs or small groups. Through completing activities in this way, it is argued, learners will obtain several benefits:

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- They can learn from hearing the language used by other members of the group.
- They will produce a greater amount of language than they would use in teacher-fronted activities.
- Their motivational level is likely to increase.
- They will have the chance to develop fluency.
- Teaching and classroom materials today consequently make use of a wide variety of small-group activities.

Today CLT can be seen as describing a set of core principles about language learning and teaching, as summarized above, assumptions that can be applied in different ways and which address different aspects of the processes of teaching and learning. Some focus centrally on the input to the learning process. Thus content-based teaching stresses that the content or subject matter of teaching drives the whole language learning process. Some teaching proposals focus more directly on instructional processes. Task-based instruction, for example, advocates the use of specially designed instructional tasks as the basis of learning. Others, such as competency-based instruction and text-based teaching, focus on the outcomes of learning and use outcomes or products as the starting point in planning to teach. Today CLT continues in its classic form as seen in the huge range of course books and other teaching resources that cite CLT as the source of their methodology. In addition, it has influenced many other language teaching approaches that subscribe to a similar philosophy of language teaching.

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